

Research

Study on Mechanical and Durability Properties of Desert Sand Brick Based on Microbial Mineralization

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Abstract: The microbial desert sand brick has the characteristics of high strength, long service life, stable performance and simple construction. However, the lack of resources has led to a reduction in natural raw materials and the implementation of farmland protection policies. Alternative materials for clay such as tailings, shale, coal, and river powder have geographical limitations, high sintering temperatures, and complex production processes. Moreover, the resources of desert sand are all over the world, the feasibility of desert sand in engineering construction has been verified by many scholars. but the use of desert sand is seldom. In order to make full use of desert sand, this research takes desert sand as the main raw material. Microbial mineralization deposition technology is a new type of biomass cement preparation method. Mineralized deposition calcium carbonate can effectively cement desert sand brick particles, thereby improving the strength of the microbial desert sand brick. Therefore, this research group proposes to combine the method of microbial mineralization with high strength and low-cost desert sand brick, and use microbial mineralization to enhance the mechanical and durability performance of the microbial desert sand brick. In this research, the mineralization deposition efficiency of microorganism KJ01 and the performance of microbial mineralization enhanced the mechanical and durability of microbial desert sand brick were tested. Based on the study of the mineralization and deposition efficiency of microorganism KJ01, the performance of desert sand brick enhanced by microbial mineralization was studied. The effects of the mixed solution of microorganisms and nutrients and the concentration of bacterial solution on the mechanical properties and durability of desert sand bricks were studied. The results show that the mixture of microorganisms and nutrients can effectively increase the compressive strength, flexural strength and softening coefficient of microbial desert sand bricks, which are increased by 1.73%, 15.68%, 28.57% and 18.52%, respectively, reducing the water absorption and the weight loss after freezing and thawing were 2.7% and 19.39%, respectively.

Keywords: Microbial Mineralization, Desert Sand, Microbial Desert Sand Brick.

1. Introduction

As we all know, brick is one of the most important components in the construction industry. Bricks all over the world are made of different materials. There are many methods for making bricks, but most of them use high-energy compression and / or high-temperature high-stress sintering. The most common method of making bricks is to burn clay at high temperature. Laterite bricks are usually placed in wooden molds, dried in the sun for 2-3 days, and then baked in an oven at 1200 ° C for 24 hours [1]. The engineering properties and physical properties of red clay bricks are different, mainly due to the difference in clay source and firing temperature. For example, Oxford's bottom clay bricks have an unfired strength of 3.5 MPa in 28 days and a fire resistance of more than 20 MPa [2]. Another method uses not only lime and cement, but also clay and ground blast furnace slag to make by-products. The bricks are cured at room temperature and the yield strength is between 2.7 and 5 MPa [3]. Alternatives to red clay bricks include lime sand bricks, which are made of a mixture of water, sand, and lime, compacted at a pressure of 20 MPa, and then autoclaved at a temperature of up to 190 ° C for 9 hours (Fang et al. People. [4]). Other methods of making soil-based building materials include adobe, cob, rammed soil and compressed adobe [5,6]. Most researchers have studied making bricks from waste materials like fly ash, sewage sludge, oven slag, quarry dust, billet scale, hazardous sludge, ceramic sludge, waste sugarcane bagasse and rice husk ashes [7,8,9,10,11]. In fact, the current trend in the world is to find materials from different sources and compositions to meet definite performance and minimize costs [12]. Sustainable development must consider the flow of energy and materials during construction, maintenance, disassembly, and material handling related to the project [13]. Microbially-induced calcite precipitation is a sustainable natural biological process. Using the metabolic capacity of bacteria, a combination of highly active urea-dissolving bacteria and a calcium source produces a cement called calcite (CaCO_3) [14]. After introducing calcite cement into the pores of the soil matrix, MIP has been widely used in foundation treatment to improve the shear strength and rigidity of the soil (15, 16, 17). In addition, Microbially-induced calcite precipitation can also be used in a variety of other applications, including environmental restoration [18], durability improvement and construction material restoration [19,20,21]. Using existing local resources and minimum materials and energy to meet the needs of society will help to adopt sustainable development methods. It is in this aspect that we think about the use of desert sand to manufacture brick based on microbial mineralization.

Desert sand is a highly available material in many countries around the world. And most of the researcher have work on it to use it in cocreate. This article summarizes a research project that develops a natural biological cementing process to produce microbial desert sand bricks. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to prepare microbial desert sand bricks and determine their mechanical properties and durability. The compressive strength, flexural strength, thermal conductivity, baulk density, softening coefficient, water absorption and freeze-thaw resistance of microbial desert sand bricks were tested, and the test results were evaluated.

2. Materials and methods

2.1.1. Materials and mixing of raw materials

The materials used for the manufacturing of bricks were desert sand, fly ash, calcium oxide, silica fume, microorganism, nutrient solution and water.

2.1.1 Desert Sand

The desert sand used in the experiment comes from the Ala Shan Desert in the Inner Mongolia Autonomous Region of China, as shown in Fig. (2-1a). Desert sand due to the changeable desert climate, under long-term wind load, the particle size of sand gradually becomes smaller and smaller, the surface is smooth and round, and the gradation is poor, the porosity is large, the activity is poor, and the surface adhesion is small. The particle size composition of the desert sand used in the test is shown in Table.

Tab. 2.1 Particle size composition of desert sand used in the test

Sieve size (mm)	4.75	2.36	1.18	0.60	0.30	0.15	<0.15
Accumulated sieve residue (%)	0	0	0	0	0	48.8	51.2

According to the standard of quality and inspection method of sand and stone for ordinary concrete (JGJ 52-2006), the fineness modulus of desert sand M_x is as follows:

$$M_x = \frac{(A_2 + A_3 + A_4 + A_5 + A_6) - 5A_1}{100 - A_1} \quad (2 - 1)$$

Where:

$A_1 \sim A_6$ -- the cumulative percentage of sieve residue of 4.75mm, 2.36mm, 1.18mm, 0.60mm, 0.30mm, 0.15mm, respectively;

M_x - fineness modulus of sand.

When $M_x = 0.7 \sim 1.5$, the sand is very fine sand; when $M_x = 1.6 \sim 2.2$, the sand is fine sand; when $M_x = 2.3 \sim 3.0$, the sand is medium sand; when $M_x = 3.1 \sim 3.7$, the sand is coarse sand. According to Table. 2-1 and Eq (2-1), we can calculate the desert sand $M_x = 1$. It is concluded that the desert sand used in this experiment is very fine sand.

2.1.2 Fly ash

The fly ash used in the test came from Grade II fly ash produced by Shanxi Jinzhong Guodian Yuci Thermal Power Co., Ltd. The chemical composition of fly ash is shown in Table.

Tab. 2.2 Chemical component of fly ash

Chemical composition	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	CaO	MgO	K ₂ O	SO ₃	Loss on ignition
Content (%)	40.43	24.63	6.68	5.82	0.65	1.22	0.61	4.62

2.1.3 Calcium oxide

The calcium oxide used in the test was quicklime. Quicklime is produced by Tianjin Jinhui Taiya Chemical Reagent Co., Ltd., with CaO content $\geq 95\%$.

2.1.4 Silica fume

The silica fume used in the test was in this study, the silica fume used is Eken920, Norwegian. SiO₂ content $\geq 85\%$, water content $\leq 3\%$, bulk density 315 kg/m³, specific surface area ≥ 15 m²/g.

2.1.5 Microorganism

The microorganism used in the experiment is the microorganism kj01 independently selected and cultivated by our research group. The microorganism was deposited in the general microbiology center of China microbial species preservation Management Committee on March 26, 2018, with the preservation number of CGMCC no.15516.

Microbial media

The ingredients of medium for KJ01 microorganism are: 1L ultra-pure water, 5g yeast powder, 4.5g Trimethylglycine, 10g tryptone, 5g ammonium sulfate, 2g glutamic acid and 10g urea. Then, the pH value of the medium was adjusted to 7.0 with 2 mol / L NaOH solution to obtain the most suitable pH value for the propagation and survival of bacteria.

2.1.6 Nutrient solution

The nutrient solution consists of urea (analytical pure), calcium nitrate (analytical pure) and ultra-pure water. The urea concentration is 1.0mol/l and the calcium nitrate concentration is 0.5mol/l.

2.1.7 Water

- (1) The water used for the culture medium and nutrient solution used for KJ01 microorganism cultivation is ultra-pure water;
- (2) The preparation of microbial sea sand blocks is tap water.

2.2. Preparation of brick specimens

Mixture proportions of raw materials for brick is shown in Table 2-6. In this study, we have three mixtures. Each mixture has two substances, one mixture is made of water, and the other mixture is made of microorganisms. In the case of a microorganism mixture, the percentage of microorganisms is 6.5%, the percentage of nutrient solution is 6.5% (by weight of raw materials); in the case of a water mixture, the percentage of water is 13% (by weight of raw materials).

Brick series	Desert Sand (%)	Fly Ash (%)	Calcium Oxid (%)	Silica Fume (%)
E01	70	5	20	5
E02	65	10	20	5
E03	60	15	20	5

Tab. 2-3 Mixture proportions of raw materials for brick manufacturing.

2.2.1. Molding and Curing of brick specimens

In order to prepare microbial desert sand bricks, as shown in the figure, the desired proportion of raw materials and the desert sand in the dry state are manually mixed for 1 minute. (Fig. 2-9a), The liquid (microorganism or water) was then added to the mixture and mixed for 5 minutes. Then fill the material into a steel mold with a size of (240 x 115 x 53) mm and compress it with a jack at a pressure of (5-8) MPa, as shown in Figure 2-9(b). As shown in Figure 2-9c, then dry cure at room temperature ($20 \pm 5^\circ \text{C}$) for 24 h, then transfer the sample to an oven and cure at temperature of ($105 \pm 5^\circ \text{C}$), for 2 days. as shown in Figure 2-9(d).

(a). Mixing process

(b). Molding process

(c). Room temperature curing process

(d). Oven curing process

Figure 2-9 Brick specimen's manufacturing

2.4. Experimental methodology

The mechanical properties and durability of the brick samples are determined according to the GB / T 2542-2012 National Standard of the People's Republic of China (Test Method for Wall Bricks) [22]. The brick samples of each mixing ratio were tested.

2.4.1. Compressive strength Test

For the compressive strength test, 10 brick samples were used. Saw the sample into two half-cut bricks. Stack the two half-cut bricks against each other, use 42.5 ordinary Portland cement slurry in the middle to bond, and use the cement slurry less than 3 mm to flatten the upper and lower sides, requiring the upper and lower sides, bond them in parallel as shown in Figure 2-11 (a), and then place them in a non-ventilated room for 3 days, and then test the compressive strength of the samples. Use a compression testing machine (Model WAW-1000KN microcomputer controlled electro-hydraulic service energy) to determine the compressive strength of the brick samples, as shown in Figure 2-11 (b). The lower pressure plate of the testing machine is supported by a spherical hinge. Place two half-cut brick samples in the center of the compressor plate and gradually apply an axial load at a rate of (4 KN / s) to observe the failure mode of the brick and the maximum load the brick can withstand. The bearing capacity is calculated according to formula (2-2).

$$\text{Compressive strength, } C = \frac{W}{A} \quad (2-2)$$

Where,

C = Compressive strength of the specimen (MPa),

W = maximum load at failure (N), indicated by the testing machine, and

A = Area under compression, (mm²).

2.4.2. Flexural Strength Test

For the modulus of rupture, the specimen consists of full-size units. Ten such samples were tested. First, soak the sample in (20 ± 5 °C) water for 24 hours, and then take it out. Wipe the surface moisture with a damp cloth, and then perform the flexural strength test. As shown in Figure 2-12, use a compression test machine (WAW-1000KN microcomputer-controlled electro-hydraulic service energy) to determine the flexural strength of the brick sample. The radius of curvature of the upper pressure roller and lower support roller is 15 mm. One of the lower support rollers is hinged and the other is fixed. The distance between the two brackets is (200 mm). Apply the load uniformly at a speed of (100 N / s) until the specimen ruptures, and record the maximum failure load P. Calculate the bending strength of each sample according to equation (2-3).

$$R_c = \frac{3PL}{2BH^2} \quad (2 - 3)$$

Where,

R_c = Flexural Strength (MPa),

P = Maximum failure load (N),

L = Span between two support (mm),

B = specimen width

H = specimen height

(a). Two half-cut brick cuts were stacked opposite

(b). Brick specimen under compressive load test

(c). Brick specimen under breaking load

Figure 2-12 Brick specimen test setup

2.4.3. Thermal Conductivity

Building bricks should also provide adequate insulation, cold and sound insulation materials. The thermal conductivity and acoustic conductivity of the brick vary greatly with the density and porosity of the brick. The dense bricks conduct heat and sound faster. As a result, their thermal and acoustic performance is very poor. The thermal conductivity of microbial desert sand bricks is determined by the TC3000E thermal conductivity meter (manufactured by Xi'an Xiaxi Electronic Technology Co., Ltd.) using the transient hot wire method (Figure 2-13), and the thermal conductivity is determined according to the Chinese specification. Hot wire method for non-metallic solid materials (GB / T 10297-2015) [23]. Commonly used thermal conductivity measurement methods include steady-state method and transient method. As a transient method, the hot wire method has been widely used to measure the thermal conductivity of gases, liquids, solids and other materials. The uncertainty of experimental measurement is less than 0.5%. The basic principle of measuring the thermal conductivity of a material by the transient hot wire method is to place a metal heating wire (ie, a hot wire) with an infinite diameter, an infinite length, and an internal temperature balance in the middle of the measured material. The hot wire serves as a linear heat source and maintains thermal equilibrium with the material under test in its initial state. If a constant heat flow is suddenly applied to the linear heat source for a period of time, an increase in temperature of the linear heat source and surrounding materials will occur. Because the temperature rise of the linear heat source is related to the thermophysical parameters

of the test material, the thermal conductivity of the material under test can be obtained by measuring the rate of temperature rise of the linear heat source. The formula for measuring the thermal conductivity of solid materials by the hot wire method is as follows:

$$\lambda = \frac{P}{4\pi L} \times \frac{1}{A} \quad (2-4)$$

$$A = \frac{\Delta\theta}{\Delta \ln t} \quad (2-5)$$

Where,

λ —Thermal conductivity of test material, W/(m·K);

P—Heating power of hot wire, W;

L—Hotline length, m;

T—Temperature of hot wire, K;

t —Heating time of corresponding temperature, s;

A— $\Delta T \sim \Delta \ln t$ Slope of linear relationship.

Before measuring the thermal conductivity of microbial desert sand bricks, first dry the microbial desert sand bricks to a constant weight in an oven at $105 \pm 5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ according to Figure 2-14, and then measure their thermal conductivity.

2.4.4. Bulk density Test

Figure 2-13 Thermal conductivity tester

For the bulk density test, the number of brick samples is 5 in full-scale units. First clean the surface of the sample, and then put the sample in an air-drying oven at $(105 \pm 5)^\circ \text{C}$ to dry to a constant weight for 2 hours, as shown in Figure 2-14. Weigh the mass (D), measure the sample size after drying twice, and take the average value to calculate the volume (V). Calculate the bulk density (P) of each sample according to (Equation (2-6)).

$$B = D/V \quad (2-6)$$

Where,

B = Bulk density, (g/m^3)

V = Volume of brick specimens, (m^3) and

D = dry weight of the specimen, (g).

2.4.5. Softening test

In order to soften the test, the overall height and width of the half brick were tested, and the average value of five samples was calculated. Immerse the sample used for the softening test in water with a temperature of $(20 \pm 5)^\circ \text{C}$, the water level is more than 20 mm above the sample, soak for 4 days as shown in Figure 2-15, then take it out and drop it on the wire mesh frame Minutes, then wring out the damp cloth and wipe off the water on the surface of the specimen. Then move the comparative sample to an air-free room with a temperature of $(20 \pm 5)^\circ \text{C}$, and leave the sample for 72 hours as an air-dried sample. The compressive strength test shall be carried out on the softened sample and the unsoftened comparative sample according to the method specified in 2.4.1. Calculate the softening coefficient according to the equation. (2-7).

$$K_f = \frac{R_f}{R_o} \quad (2-7)$$

Where,

K_f = softening coefficient

R_f = the average value of compressive strength after softening, (MPa) and

R_o = the average value of compressive strength of comparative samples, (MPa).

2.4.6. Water Absorption

The unit's full-size bricks were tested and the average of five samples was calculated. First, the sample is dried to a constant temperature of $105 \pm 5^\circ \text{C}$ in an oven, then weighed, and then

the dried, cooled sample is immersed in clean water at a temperature of $(20 \pm 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C})$ for 24 hours, as shown in Figure 2. -16. After 24 hours, remove the sample, wipe the surface water with a damp cloth and weigh it. Weigh each sample within 5 minutes after removing the sample from the water, and calculate the water absorption according to formula (2-8).

$$A = \left(\frac{W-D}{D}\right) \times 100 \quad (2-8)$$

Where,

A = Water absorption, %

D = dry weight of the sample, (g) and

W = saturation weight (g) of the sample after immersion in cold water for 24 hours.

2.4.7. Freezing and Thawing

In order to check the freeze-thaw resistance of brick samples, the samples were placed under freeze-thaw conditions according to GB / T 2542-2012 [80]. The entire height and width of the half-brick unit were tested for 20 samples of each mixture, of which 10 samples were used for freeze-thaw testing and 10 samples were used for thawing compressive strength testing. First, dry the sample to a constant weight in an oven at $(105 \pm 5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C})$, and then weigh it. Then immerse the sample in water at a temperature of $(15-20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C})$, dry it after 24 hours, wipe off the surface moisture with a damp cloth and weigh it. Then place it in a refrigerator with a large space of more than 20 mm placed side by side and freeze it at $(-15 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} \sim -20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C})$ for 5 hours, as shown in Figure 2-17. Then take it out and put it into $(15 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} \pm 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C})$ water to melt for 3h. The samples were kept under freezing and thawing conditions for 50 cycles. After each 5 freezing and thawing cycles, weigh the sample and check it for damage during freezing and thawing, such as frost cracks, missing edges, angle drop, peeling, etc. After the freeze-thaw cycle, move the sample into a blast drying oven, dry it to a constant weight for 2 days, and then weigh it. According to the provisions of 2.4.1, the compressive strength test shall be carried out on the dried samples and the samples without freeze-thaw. The strength loss rate and mass loss rate values are calculated according to Equation (2-9).

$$P_m = \frac{P_0 - P_1}{P_0} \times 100 \quad (2-9)$$

Where,

P_m = Strength loss rate (%),

P_m = Strength of the specimen before Freeze-thaw (MPa) and

P_m = Specimen strength after freeze-thaw (MPa).

Fig. 2-15 Brick specimens submerged in water for water absorption test

Figure 2-15 Brick specimens submerged in water for softening test

Figure 2-17 Brick specimen in the refrigerator freezing and thawing test

2.4.8. Microscopic analysis

In this study, the instrument used for SEM microanalysis was the JSM-7100F scanning electron microscope produced by JEOL.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Physical Properties of microbial desert sand brick

3.1.1 Color

The most common building brick color is red. It can range from dark red to light red to light yellow and purple. Dark red indicates excessive burning of bricks, and yellow indicates excessive burning of bricks. Figure 3-1 shows the microbial desert sand brick MDSB and the desert sand brick composed of water DSBW. The color of microbial desert sand brick MDSB is charcoal gray, while the desert sand brick composed of water DSBW is ash-gray.

Figure 3-1 Brick specimen color

- (a). Desert sand brick which is composed of water DSBW
- (b). Microbial Desert Sand Brick MDSB

3.1.2 Bulk density

The density or weight per unit volume of the brick depends mainly on the type of material used and the method of brick formation. For standard bricks, the density varies (1600-1900 kg/m³). Figure 3-2 shows the results within the bulk density (1800-1900 kg/m³) of brick samples. The amount of the mixed solution of microorganism and nutrients affects the degree of cementation of microbial desert sand bricks. As the amount of mixed solution increases, the bulk density gradually increases. The increase ranges of bulk density in E01, E02, and E03 are 1.32%, 1.48%, and 1.73%, respectively. According to the national standard GBT 21144-2007 (solid concrete bricks) of the Republic of China, the bricks are grade B bricks and are classified according to the density grade [24].

Figure 3-2 Bulk density (Kg/cum)

3.1.3 Thermal Conductivity

Thermal conductivity is a measure of the flow of heat through a uniform material sample of known thickness when a known temperature difference is applied to the two surfaces. The results are expressed in Watts / meter Kelvin ($W / m * K.$). The thermal conductivity results are shown in the table. The results show that the thermal conductivity of the microbial desert sand brick E01 mixture is low, 0.8578 ($W / m * K.$), And the thermal conductivity of the desert sand brick E01 mixture (DSBW) composed of water has high thermal conductivity, equal to 0.9613 ($W / m * K.$). As the content of fly ash in the microorganism mixture increases, the thermal conductivity increases, and as the content of fly ash in the water mixture increases, the thermal conductivity decreases, as shown in Figure 3-3.

Figure 3-3 Thermal Conductivity (W/m*K)

3.2 Mechanical properties of Microbial Desert Sand Brick

Under the mechanical properties of bricks, including compressive strength and flexural strength. The mechanical properties of the brick samples were determined according to the National Standard GB / T 2542-2012 (Test Method for Wall Bricks) of the People's Republic of China [22]. Table 2-3 shows the brick samples for each mixing ratio.

3.2.1 Compressive strength

The compressive strength results of brick samples are shown in Table 3-1. The results reported the average of five brick samples, the coefficient of variation was less than 10%. The results show that the E03 mixture of microbial desert sand bricks MODSB has a higher compressive strength, equivalent to MU 30, while the E01 mixture of desert sand bricks composed of water DSBW has the lowest compressive strength, which is equal to MU 25 level, according to (Solid concrete Brick) of GBT 21144-2007 [24]. The results show that the

compressive strength can be improved by increasing the amount of fly ash in the mixture, as shown in Figure 3-4. The amount of the mixed solution of microorganism and nutrients affects the degree of cementation of microbial desert sand bricks. As the amount of mixed solution increases, the compressive strength of the sample gradually increases. In the E01, E02, and E03 mixtures, the compressive strength increases by 9.25%, 11.0%, and 15.68%, respectively.

Figure 3-4 Compressive Strength (MPa)

Tab. 3-1 Compressive strength test results

Brick Series	Compressive strength (MPa)		Improve of Compressive strength By MM (%)
	(DSBW)	(MODSB)	
E01	22.28	24.55	9.25
E02	23.54	26.45	11.0
E03	24.09	28.57	15.68

3.2.2 Flexural strength

Table 3-2 shows the bending strength results of the desert sand brick samples. The results reported the average value of ten brick samples, the coefficient of variation was less than 15%. The results show that

the E03 mixture of microbial desert sand bricks MDSB has a higher bending strength, while the E01 mixture of desert sand bricks composed of water DSBW has the lowest bending strength. The amount of the mixed solution of microorganism and nutrients affects the degree of cementation of microbial desert sand bricks. As the amount of mixed solution increases, the flexural strength of the sample gradually increases. As shown in Figure 3-5, in the E01, E02, and E03 mixtures, the bending strength increased by 16%, 25%, and 28.57%, respectively. According to the national standard GB / T 25993-2010 (permeable bricks and permeable bricks) of the People's Republic of China, the flexural strength should not be less than 2.4 MPa [25]. And according to ASTM C67, the minimum requirement of brick flexural strength is 0.65 MPa [26].

Figure 3-5 Flexural Strength (MPa)

Tab. 3-2 Flexural strength Test Results

Brick Series	Flexural strength (MPa)		Improve of flexural strength By MM (%)
	DSBW	MDSB	
E01	2.1	2.5	16
E02	2.4	3.2	25
E03	2.5	3.5	28.57

3.4 Durability properties of Microbial Desert Sand Brick

Based on the durability of bricks, it is understandable that when bricks are used in buildings, they remain constant and strong for the longest time. The durability of the brick samples can be determined according to the National Standard GB / T 2542-2012 (Test Method for Wall Bricks) of the People's Republic of China [22]. Table 2-3 shows the brick samples for each mixing ratio.

3.4.1 Softening test

The softening coefficient is used to measure the change of compressive strength of bricks before and after soaking. Table 3-3 shows the results of changes in the softening coefficient and compressive strength of brick samples after the softening test. The softening coefficient of MDSB microbial brick samples is in the range of (0.76-0.81), while the softening coefficient of DSBW brick samples is in the range of (0.66-0.80). The results show that by increasing the amount of fly ash in the DSBW mixture, the softening coefficient will decrease, but on the contrary, by increasing the amount of fly ash in the MDSB mixture, the softening coefficient will increase. The results show that the E03 mixture of MDSB has a higher softening coefficient, and the E03 mixture of DSBW has the lowest softening coefficient, as shown in Figure 3-6. According to GBT 21144-2007 (solid concrete bricks), the softening coefficient should not be less than 0.5, [24].

Tab. 3-3 Softening Test Results

Brick Series	Softening Coefficient		C.S before Softening Test (MPa)		C.S after Softening Test (MPa)	
	DSBW	MDSB	DSBW	MDSB	DSBW	MDSB
E01	0.8	0.76	22.28	24.55	17.82	18.24
E02	0.7	0.78	23.54	26.45	16.48	20.63
E03	0.66	0.81	24.09	28.57	16.43	23.14

Figure 3-6 After soaking the brick specimens,
Softening Coefficient and Compressive Strength (MPa)

3.4.2 Water absorption

See Table 3-4 for water absorption test results. It is one of the important parameters that characterize the performance of bricks, and is also regarded as an indicator of durability and porosity. Low water absorption indicates that the brick has high density, weather resistance and acceptable permeability [28,89]. Water absorption is the main factor affecting the durability of bricks [27]. All brick samples tested showed (12.39–12.95) % water absorption, as shown in Figure 3-7, the results show that the water absorption rate of MDSB is smaller than that of DSBW. According to GBT 21144-2007 (Solid Concrete Brick) [24], the water absorption should be less than or equal to 13%, and the classification should be based on the density level of the brick (equal to B level). The durability of the brick depends on the water absorption rate [29]. In many parts of the world, water absorption between 20% and 30% is acceptable [28,30].

Tab. 3-4 Water absorption test results

Brick Series	Water absorption (%)	
	DSBW	MDSB

E01	12.53	12.39
E02	12.74	12.63
E03	12.93	12.89

Figure 3-7 Water absorption (%)

3.4.3 Freeze and thaw resistance

Table 3-5 shows the freeze-thaw resistance test results of brick samples after 50 cycles. The interaction between materials and climatic effects plays a key role in the freeze-thaw durability of bricks [32]. Due to expansion, unfilled holes can be filled with unfrozen liquid. If the pore volume is less than the water swelling volume [31], failure will occur. During the freeze-thaw cycle, the water in the hole freezes and expands. In the process of changing from liquid to solid, water swells by about 9% [33]. Figures 3-8 show the weight loss of brick samples due to freeze-thaw after 50 cycles. It was observed that the brick samples showed weight loss in the range (1.2-0.78%) after 50 cycles. The weight loss of the MDSB sample is less than the DSBW sample. According to GBT 21144-2007 [24], It is considered unacceptable if the sample ruptures during freeze-thaw cycles, lacks edges, decreases in angle, peels off, and increases weight loss by 5% or strength loss by 25%. The weight loss was less than 5%, no cracks, no edges, no inclination, no

flaking was observed in the brick samples after 50 freeze-thaw cycles, and Figure 3-10 shows the images of the brick samples before and after freezing and thawing. Water penetrates during thawing period and expands during freezing. In samples with high pore volume, high stress due to freeze-thaw was observed, resulting in reduced durability [35,36]. Generally, freeze-thaw resistance depends on the porosity of the sample [34].

Tab. 3-5 Freeze and thaw resistance test results

Brick Series	Weight loss due to freeze-thaw after 50 cycles (%)	
	(DSBW)	(MODSB)
E01	1.18	1.07
E02	1.11	0.88
E03	0.98	0.79

Figure 3-8 Weight loss due to freeze-thaw after 50 cycles (%)

3.5 SEM microscopic analysis

Figure 3-10 is a photomicrograph of microbial desert sand MDSB brick and desert sand brick composite of water DSBW. It can be seen that the microbial brick sample has a different morphology compared to the desert sand brick composite water. Micrograph of crystals deposited by bacterial solution. It can be seen from the figure that the crystals are mainly wrapped by microorganisms, similar to calcite in calcium carbonate. The massive crystals are stacked and overlapped with each other, and the crystal surface is relatively rough, but there is microorganism KJ01 The trace left by the activity is that the particle size of the crystal is basically below $10\ \mu\text{m}$, which belongs to the small granular crystal; Figure 3-10 (b), (c) and (f) are the microscopic figure of the crystal deposited by the mineralization of the bacterial solution. It can be seen from the figure that the crystal form is a massive crystal group, the accumulation state is the center of the large-sized crystal, and there are many small-sized crystals attached on the surface, compared with the crystal deposited by the mineralized bacteria solution, the crystal particle size deposited by the mineralized bacteria solution is larger, and there are more small-sized crystals attached to the surface of the large-sized crystal. It can be seen from the whole that with the bacterial solution, the crystal morphology deposited by microorganism KJ01 mineralization shows an increasing trend, and at the same time, it also increases the formation of small-size crystals. These small-size crystals are massive and layered, randomly distributed and wrapped on the large-size crystals. In the process of microorganism mineralization and deposition, microorganisms play the following roles: (a) secrete urease, decompose urea, generate CO_3^{2-} , (b) provide nucleation point for mineralization and deposition. When the number of microorganisms is small, the nucleation sites of mineralized deposition will be smaller, and the crystal grain size of mineralized deposition on the limited nucleation sites will also be smaller, and the crystal surface will be relatively flat; when the number of microorganisms is large, the number of urease secreted by microorganisms will increase, and the crystals will overlap with each other. As the number of ureases secreted by microorganisms increases, the crystals will continue to deposit and grow, making the crystal whole However, due to the large number of microorganisms, individual microorganisms independently mineralized and deposited, resulting in a series of small-sized crystals.

Mixture	Composite of water	Composite of Microorganism
E01		
	(a)	(b)
E02		
	(c)	(d)
E03		
	(e)	(f)

Figure 3-10 SEM images (5000 times)

4. Conclusions

Microbial building materials are of great significance for the development of green building materials. In this research, the preliminary application research of microbial mineralization deposited in the preparation of desert sand brick, but there is still a lot of research work that needs to continue to advance, in-depth and improve microbes and accelerating carbonation effects on microorganism desert sand brick. In this research, the properties of Microbial desert

sand bricks were investigated. Based on the characteristics of the mineralized deposit of microorganism KJ01, the mineralized deposited calcium carbonate crystals are used as biological cement to enhance the performance of desert sand brick. The effect on the activity of microbe KJ01 urease and the efficiency of mineralization and deposition, the preparation factors of microorganism desert sand brick on compressive strength, flexural strength, water absorption, softening coefficient, freezing and thawing resistance and thermal conductivity of the desert sand brick. The mixture of microorganisms and nutrients can increase the bulk density, compressive strength and flexural strength of the microorganism desert sand brick, reduce the water absorption of the desert sand brick, and have little effect on the thermal conductivity, softening coefficient and resistance against freezing-thawing of the desert sand brick. With the mixture of microorganism when the amount of fly ash is 15%, the bulk density, compressive strength, flexural strength and the increase of softening coefficient is 1.73%, 15.68%, 28.57% and 18.52% respectively, the reduction of water absorption and thermal conductivity is 0.31%, and 2.74% respectively, the and the weight loss after 50 cycles of freezing and thawing reduce to 19.39%. The incorporation of high concentration bacterial solution and calcium peroxide is beneficial to enhance the performance of the desert sand brick. the best maintenance method of the microorganism desert sand brick is dry and wet cycle maintenance, the optimal maintenance temperature is 20 ± 5 °C, curing for 24h and oven dry at temperature is 105 ± 5 °C for 48h respectively, the bulk density reaches 1869.74 kg / m^3 , the compressive strength and flexural strength reaches 28.5MPa and 3.5 MPa respectively, the thermal conductivity is 0.9, and the water absorption rate is 12.89%. and the softening coefficient is 0.81, the weight loss after 50 cycles of freezing and thawing is 0.79%.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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